

The Role of Education in Overcoming Violence against Women

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"We will not accept that there is no end to endemic violence against girls and women and we will work persistently, relentlessly for the change we need at a government level, at an institutional level, at an economic level, [and] at a personal – attitudinal level – to bring that change about" Justine Greening, 4 March 2013.

Introduction

The Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women defines "violence against women" as "any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life." The Declaration requires States to "exercise due diligence to prevent, investigate by national legislation, punish acts of violence against women, whether those acts are perpetrated by the State or by private persons." Violence against women is an issue that is spoken and discussed worldwide because of the consequences that violence against women makes to its victims and society. Irrespective of caste, creed, religion, class, place (rural or urban), we can see violence against women. Are women safe worldwide? is the question raised by women activists, and when we ask our self, the answer is no. Women today have high chances of being victims of violence like Acid attack, Honour killing, women and child trafficking, rape, sexual and all forms of harassment, etc.

Even before birth, the girl babies are aborted as many societies like India consider them as a burden. They are not safe, and their right to be born on the earth is not sure for them. Women activists, Ngo's, and other agencies working on women through their discussion and meetings insist that violence against women is a human rights concern. If a woman is a victim of violence, it takes long years to overcome.

“Statistics show that offenders are more likely to choose victims who have been previously assaulted.” (New York Times September 2018). This paper discusses about the issue of violence against women in the Indian scenario with the examples from newspaper cuttings and NCRB report and highlights the role of education in overcoming violence against women.

The Indian Scenario on Violence Against Women

India is tied up with caste and patriarchal culture where the woman is given a secondary position when compared to men. Even though women are achieving in their fields, getting awards still the cultural norms in Indian society stresses her to oblige men. Women are less aware of the issue of violence against women and are hesitating to approach police stations or any Non Governmental Organization helping women. According to the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) in the year 2015-2016 says that an estimated 99.1% of sexual violence cases are unreported, and in most such instances, the perpetrator is the husband of the victim. Women, fear of what their family members would say, what their friends and relatives think of them and their family.

Indian society vests the responsibility of maintaining the honour of the family to women, and hence, there are unreported cases of violence against women. In India, Women think about their future life and their children continue to stay in an abusive relationship and accept violent acts committed to them. Threatening to women like killing, pornography, etc. continue to exist if they file a case or tell it to others. The victims of violence against women do not get adequate support in terms of health, legal, economy, etc.

Incidents of Violence against Women in India

NORTH

UP: Dalit woman set on fire by moneylenders, 2 arrested

Allahbad: A 40-year-old Dalit woman was allegedly set on fire by moneylenders in a village in UP's Ballia district Thursday. Two persons were arrested in connection with the case. Reshmi Devi was sleeping at her house in Jajauli village when a group of people poured kerosene over her and set her on fire, police said. "The incident occurred around 2 am on Friday. Her screams woke up her family who rushed her to a nearby hospital. She suffered 40 per cent burn injuries and is being treated in BHU trauma centre in Varanasi where she was shifted to," SP, Ballia, Anil Kumar said. **ENS**

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The news is about the money lenders who set fire on the Dalit woman by pouring kerosene on her body while she was sleeping at her home in the night. This example shows that women are not safe anywhere, anytime, whether she is alone or with their family members. Such incidents pluck the right to live in society. There are chances for the Dalit woman being, again and again, the victim of violence against women. It will take a long time for the Dalit women to recover and lead a peaceful life.

KATHUA CHARGESHEET

In J&K child gangrape, rituals, a chilling invite and a police cover-up

MUZAMIL JALEEL
NEW DELHI, APRIL 10

THE EIGHT-YEAR-OLD was gangraped thrice inside the Devasthan or prayer hall, after the masteemirdhad "performed rituals". One of the rapists was called from Meerut to "satisfy his lust". The girl was confined using relatives, then strangled and hit on the head twice with a stone — "in order to make sure" she was dead. But not before another accused, a police personnel, asked the others to "wait because he wanted to rape" her one last time.

And all this, to "dislodge" a group of Bakherwal Muslim nomads from Rasana village in Kathua near Jammu.

These are just some of the chilling details in the 18-page chargesheet filed Monday by J&K Police's Crime Branch against the eight accused in the rape and murder of the girl who went missing from near her house in Rasana on January 10 — her body

On Monday, lawyers tried to stop filing of chargesheet

was found seven days later in the forests nearby.

In the days that followed, the chargesheet states, the accused paid Rs 15 lakh as a bribe to local policemen who knew where the girl was kept and helped cover up the crime initially.

The killing had sparked outrage across J&K with the government handing over the case to the Crime Branch following protests from the Bakherwal community. The case took a communal turn in Kathua, where an outfit called Hindu Ekta Manch was set up by politicians

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FROM THE FRONT PAGE

J&K gangrape

In support of the accused. Among these who have the former served Jammu and Kashmir Chief Minister Mehbooba Mufti's cabinet.

According to the chargesheet, the masteemirdhad behind the case at a hand of a friend named Nargis Khan who is among the eight arrested, along with his son Vishal Jangora and nephew, believed to be a police.

The Crime Branch had also arrested Special Police Officers (SPOs) Desapak Khurana and Sunder Kumar, a Rasana resident, and two, Assistant Sub-Inspector Anand Datta and Head Constable Tik Raj in the case. Datta and Raj were arrested on charges of attempting to destroy evidence.

According to the chargesheet, the girls father Mohd Yaseen lodged a complaint on January 12 at the magistrade that his daughter who "had gone for studying horse with her brother about 1230 hrs on January 10 had not returned. A FIR was lodged and police arrested Ram's nephew, leading to a headline of 'Cover-up by the Bakherwal community. On January 23, the case was transferred to the Crime Branch.

The chargesheet states that Ram manufactured the conspiracy to kidnap and rape and kill the girl, issues that the masteemirdhad and the juvenile "part of the conspiracy and assign different tasks separately and individually".

"The police also got the five doctors who were to file Medical Report Form A on January 7 evening, and purchased one hundred tablets of mifepristone tablets by showing the prescription of his uncle, who has a psychiatric problem and is under treatment, although the work was as per the prescription issued available with him. He gave him Fipinil 0.375 mg instead of the evidence written on the prescription, the chargesheet states.

On the same day, says Ram said his

nephew to "kidnap" the girl who "often comes to a friend's house behind their house or grazing her horses". Subsequently, the juvenile "started scientific plan" worked out by Ram and Jangora with "nephew Kumar/Manish, his close friend and asked for his help".

On January 10, the juvenile called the girl asking about her horses. He told her that "he had seen her house and led her to the jungle". The girl also called accused Ram. Seeing some trouble, the victim tried to flee but the juvenile stopped her by catching hold of her neck and covered her mouth with one of his hands and pushed her and she fell on the ground," the chargesheet says.

The victim fell unconscious and was raped by the juvenile in the jungle. The masteemirdhad also attempted to rape her. They took her and kept her inside the Devasthan under the table covered with plastic mats and then covered her," it says.

On the next day, the chargesheet says, the "parents of the girl reached the Devasthan and enquired from Ram about the whereabouts of their missing daughter, who told them that she may have gone to some relative's house". The girl's father and uncle still had been confirmed as kept hidden by them on the same day, according to the chargesheet.

"Khatuna and the juvenile opened the Devasthan and separated the girl by pushing relatives into her mouth and forced her to consume substances",

"On January 11, the juvenile informed another accused Vishal Jangora about the kidnaping of the girl telephonically and asked him to return from Meerut to see he wanted to satisfy his lust," the chargesheet says.

By noon on January 11, says Jangora reached Rasana at Ram. At around 8.30 am, the juvenile again went to the Devasthan and advised the juvenile to take away the girl while she was unconscious with empty stomach," the chargesheet says.

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Khatuna came to the house of accused Saaji Ram with another police official named Rishi Kumar, Jangora advised the juvenile to ensure administrative orders and to ensure the victim's name.

"During investigation, it appeared that the accused had already done the accused police officials to confide and settled the deal with them," it says.

The chargesheet says that Akbar Qasabdar, who was part of the search party, had asked Ram to let the police know the location of the girl. He said that he had through the juvenile's member, it says.

On January 12, the chargesheet says, "as a result of Jangora's plea, work and accused Ram went to the Devasthan where Ram performed rituals". Later, it says, Jangora "raped the minor girl, thereafter the juvenile also raped her".

After keeping the girl in the prayer hall for days, the chargesheet says, Ram told the other accused that it was time to kill her and "dump her body in the forest".

"The accused Manish, Vishal and Jangora took the victim from the Devasthan to a nearby forest," accused Raj said that the juvenile "walked as he wanted to rape the girl before she is killed," the chargesheet says.

Describing the murder, the chargesheet states, "After committing the heinous act of rape on the minor victim, the accused Jangora kept her head on his left hand and started applying force with his hands on her neck, only to kill her. Khurana was unsuccessful in killing her, the juvenile killed her by pressing his knees against her back while an anguishing the girl by applying force on both the ends of her eardrums, thereafter, the accused, in order to make sure that the victim is dead, hit her twice on head with stones".

The body was dumped in the prayer hall as the accused and another friend who was involved in the case on January 11, the chargesheet says. Ram "killed" the other accused who "saw the body in the jungle".

The paper cutting says about the sensational news that shocked India, the gang rape of 8-year-old girl in the temple premises in India. The above incidents show that the perpetrators do not have humanity and this incident is a challenge to many people's misconception saying dressing of girls attract boys, the girl's behaviour that makes incidents of violence towards men.

Incidents of Violence against Women

The National Crime Records bureau which records the crime rates says that in ten years there is a drastic raise on crime against women. The table below is the comparison of incidents of crimes against women between the years 2007-2016.

Crimes against women	% of change 2007-2016
Total crimes against women	83
Rape	88
Cruelty by husband or his relatives	45
Assault with intent to outrage modesty	119

Source: NCRB

The NCRB in news click report on December 2, 2017, says that “The total crime rate number of crimes per one lakh of the population—against women has gone up from 16.3 in 2007 to 53 in 2016. Rapes have risen by 88% since 2007, in terms of incidences, while the crime rate has spiked from 1.8 to 6.3. Crimes under the category of ‘Assault on Women with Intent to Outrage her Modesty’ have seen a 119% increase. This category, covered under Section 354, was expanded in 2013 to include four new crimes. These crimes are Sexual Harassment (Sec 354A), Assault or Use of Criminal Force to Women with Intent to Disrobe (Sec 354 B), Voyeurism (Sec 354C) and Stalking (Sec 354D).

Back in 2007, the rate of crimes recorded under Section 354 was 3.4, which rose to 13.8 in 2016. While there has been a 45% rise in incidences of ‘Cruelty by Husband or his Relatives’ (Sec 498A). The NCRB says that the increase in crime rates is also an indication that more woman has come forward to report the incidents of crime. The ambit of ‘crime against women’ under the Indian Penal Code (IPC) has been expanded—after the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act 2013 was passed for the purpose to include unconsidered crimes earlier. For example, the acid attack was not a crime in 2007. Further, the NCRB says that the conviction rates are low. In 2016, the crime rate was 18.9 percent.”

The report gives a clear picture of the situation of India regarding violence against women and indicates that serious effort has to be made to curb violence against women.

The Role of Education in Overcoming Violence against Women

Education is a tool to develop an individual and make him/her independent. The human being is educated, he/she attains the leadership qualities, in making the decision-making process, creates the capacity to earn. Attitudes can easily be formed by exposure from family, neighbourhood, peers, and media. It can be changed by education as it expands one's knowledge, and educational institutions provide rational space to understand and develop positive attitudes.

Education plays an important role in educating the rights of women for both male and female. This makes women realize gender disparity and tackle it. Through Gender sensitization program individuals are educated on gender roles and, educating male that ill-treatment of women is violence and there is no separate role for male and female. These programs change the thought pattern in the minds, which leads to matured young generations. From the early school years it must be started. Separate classes on gender sensitization can be taught in schools and colleges.

Education helps to analyze an individual who is right and wrong and thus can change the view of male about female and teaches the male that any thought of committing a violent act on female can be changed and makes the male think that it is wrong to commit violent acts against women. Values can be inculcated on individuals through value education classes. Education teaches girls women how to handle a situation if they are facing a violent act by their counterpart bravely, for example, educating them in martial arts. Education is a tool in curbing violence against by creating Gender just society.

Conclusion

Violence against Women is a serious issue that makes women be always in fear and destroys the physical and mental well being of women. It stops the mobility of women and pucks the rights of women such as the right to speak, the right to live safely, the right to choose which in turn stops the holistic development of the society In order to end violence against women Government, Non Governmental agencies, activists should join hands together to end violence against women. They should work on interventions to stop violence against women like Group training (for boys and girls through role-play, video shows about the issue and how to handle it). Identify Harmful Traditional Practice in the community (like Female Genital Mutilation, Child Marriage, etc.).Community mobilization (mobilizing the people in the community by making them aware of the consequence of Violence against women and act towards stopping violent acts on women) There is all ways, and interventions in ending violence against women and education is a powerful weapon to end violence against women. Women irrespective of caste, creed, class, religion should stand together in fighting against violence.

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